

A NEW ATTACHEMENT FOR COMPOSITE TUBES IN TORSION
THE SLASHED, PRESTRESSED POLYGON FITTING.

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ABSTRACT

Non-circular GFRP- and CFRP-tubes under torque loads have been investigated by theory and tests at the Institute for Aircraft Design (IFB), University of Stuttgart.

The pass of the torque in a composite tube can be realized with polygon-formed tubes as a plugged connection. The transmission of the torque results only from the closing shape. To increase the maximum torque load a new fitting element has been developed. In tests the slashed prestressed polygon fitting element has been qualified with pressure films.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the paper some informations will be given to the development of polygonal formed GFRP/CFRP - tubes and the testing and computing of the fitting interface. The tubes have been developed to have an alternative fitting element - next to bolted or adhered elements - for tubes under torque load. The tubes with non-circular formed sections require extensive tests to evaluate

- stress-/strain-behaviour
- the critical buckling load and
- the behaviour in vibration.

The pass of the torque moment in the composite tube can be realized as a plugged connection. The transmission of the torque results only from the closing shape. A secondary advantage of this fitting is that a longitudinal adjustment is possible during assembling.

The exploration of the interactions between the flange and the tube in the fitting area has been done

- by recording the specific rotation between the flange and the tube with an inductive displacement pick-up.
- by measuring the hoop strain with strain gauges.
- by determining the contact pressure, using a pressure film.
- by computing the fitting area with the method of FINITE ELEMENTS (FE).

2. FORM DESCRIPTION

The form of a polygon can be described by the following equations [1]:

$$X_{Poly} = 0.5 d_m \cos(\alpha) - e \cos(n\alpha) \cos(\alpha) - ne \sin(n\alpha) \sin(\alpha) \quad (1)$$

$$Y_{Poly} = 0.5 d_m \sin(\alpha) - e \cos(n\alpha) \sin(\alpha) + ne \sin(n\alpha) \cos(\alpha) \quad (2)$$

The parameters are defined as (see Fig. 1)

d_m = medium diameter
 $= d_{inside} + 2e$

e = eccentricity
 (difference between the circle and polygon form)

n = number of edges

Fig. 1: parameter definition at a 3-edged polygon form.

Only through the variation of the 3 parameters d_m , e and n different forms, for example an eccentric circle form, an elliptic form or 3- or 4-edged polygon forms can be created (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Review of the forms, given with the equations (1), (2).

Ordinary, the forms are produced in a grinding process. There is only one restriction. The parameter e/d_m has to be smaller than $1/2(n-1)$.

For qualifying the plugged connection, tests were done with two different 3-edged polygon forms ($d_m = \text{const.}$, $e_1 < e_2$, $n=3$). The eccentricity e_2 was nearby the maximum eccentricity e_{max} . A result, done with non-prestressed flanges, was that the specific rotations could be reduced by using a form, which was more pointed. But with a section form given by e smaller than e_{max} it was not possible to bring the specific rotation down to zero. So, it has been decided to develop and produce hypercritical section forms in a milling process, with a numerical controlled machine.

A hypercritical form is given through $e > e_{\text{max}}$. In this case normally there are loops over the polygon edges, which are growing by increasing the eccentricity (see Fig. 3).

Fig. 3: Example for 4-edged hypercritical polygon forms.

For realizing hypercritical forms the polygon form has been computed with a step size of 1° . The loops over the edges have been eliminated with a software programme, so that you get forms with very pointed edges.

3. OPTIMIZATION OF A PLUGED, POLYGONAL FITTING

For qualifying the fitting the specific rotation and the energy dissipation has been found out for the following 4 test forms:

Fig. 4: Section forms, which have been produced and used in tests.

The energy dissipation for the plugged connection and the composite tube has been defined as the difference between a loop of loading and release (see Fig. 5).

The evaluation of the hysteresis has been defined for a positive torque moment loop. The curve is marked, that there is no permanent displacement within a turn. The hysteresis is the result of the visco-elastic resin behaviour and the specific rotation of the plugged connection. It is not caused by a laminate failure.

Fig. 5: Definition of the energy-dissipation, at a torque loop.

For the non-prestressed forms the following test-values have been registered:

	PQ_1		PQ_2		PQ_3		PQ_4	
torque moment [Nm]:	200	500	200	500	200	500	200	500
max. specific rot. [°]:	3.9	7.7	2.5	4.9	1.7	2.8	2.0	3.5
energy diss. [Nm]:	4.89	30.1	1.52	9.95	0.98	5.49	1.73	9.59

tube-length: 700mm, laminate-pattern: centre part: 2 mm ± 45°-GFRP;
fitting: CFRP-bandage: 6 90°-layers, staggered.

For exploring the influence of the tolerance between the flange and the tube, a slashed polygonal fitting has been developed. This fitting element has been deduced from an ordinary 3-edged polygonal fitting. The form has been disjointed starting from the flat sides to the middle of the section. By using a centric clamping-cone it's possible to generate initial stresses of variable magnitude between the fitting element and the composite tube (see Fig. 6).

Fig. 6: Drawing of a splitted, polygonal fitting.

Between the pre-stress moment M_V and the contact pressure the following relationship can be present, for the form PQ_2.

M_V [Nm]:	15	35	55	75
p_{max} [N/mm ²]:	11	26	42	57

To find out the most effective pre-stress value and laminate pattern the following 3 tubes have been tested.

fiber: E-glass, T300
 resin: L20/SL
 polygon form: PQ_2

(x,y) = position of the strain gauge.

(x') = position of the inductive displacement pick-up.

test-tube	α_i [°]	t_i [mm]	α_m [°]	t_m [mm]	α_o [°]	t_o [mm]	t_t [mm]
VQ_1:	90	0.64 (5)	± 45	1.32 (4)	90	0.64 (5)	2.6
VQ_2:	90	1.78 (15)	± 45	1.34 (4)	90	0.68 (5)	3.8
VQ_3:	90	0.62 (5)	± 45	1.32 (4)	90	1.86 (15)	3.8

i=inner, m=middle, o=out, t=total

(.....) number of layers

Fig. 6: Description of the test tubes for registrating the energy dissipation and specific rotation.

In the tests the following strains ϵ_0 have been found as results of the pre-stressing ($M_V=15 \text{ Nm} \dots 45 \text{ Nm}$) and the strains $\Delta\epsilon$ as the difference of the maximum and minimum strains registrated during a $\pm 200 \text{ Nm}$ cycle. in each case for the strain gauge 1, 2 and 3.

10000 $\mu\text{m/m} = 1\%$ strain.

The figures above show the following results:

- The strain maximum can be found, for each value of the pre-stress is at the flange-side of the tube (strain gauge position 1).
- The strains have a minimum in the middle of the fitting length and grow up to the end of the flange.
- With the number of circumferential layers the hoop strains come down. For reducing the specific rotation and to get a minimum of the circ. strains the best position for the 90° -layers is at the inside of the laminate pattern.
- With the magnitude of the pre-stress the specific rotation comes down. In parallel with that the hoop strain, resulted from the torque, have a minimum.

Tests done with pre-stressed fitting elements, given by the section form

PQ_2 and PQ_3 shows, that although by using pre-stressed elements, the best form is the form with the largest eccentricity value. The difference of the energy dissipation measured by a pre-stress moment of 55 Nm and a torque of 500 Nm was about 50%.

4. CONTACT PRESSURE AT A PLUGED. POLYGONAL FITTING ELEMENT.

Next to the specific rotation the magnitude and the curve of the contact pressure is a criterion for the fitting quality. The contact pressure has been found out

- in tests by using a pressure film and
- by computing

In this paper only the results found by tests will be given.

The basics of the pressure film are, that two films, one with a colour developer layer and the second, a microcapsule layer with the colour forming material, are brought together and with the magnitude of the pressure the film is coloured itself. The colour intensity is representative for the maximum pressure value which has been reached for one time during the test. The film has a thickness of 0.1 mm and is very flexible. So there is no problem to turn it around the polygon form. For the tests polygonal fittings have been produced with 0.2 mm amount of undersize.

Pressure films have to be chosen corresponding to the expected pressure range:

	pressure range [N/mm ²]	
Typ A:	0.5 - 2	super low pressure film
Typ B:	2 - 7	low pressure film
Typ C:	7 - 25	medium pressure film
Typ D:	25 - 70	high pressure film

For every film a reference curve for the relation of colouring and pressure magnitude can be given. This line is convenient for a quick, qualitative analyse without using any technical auxiliary, because the curve is nearly linear in a wide range (see Fig. 7).

Fig. 7: Represented is the relation between colouring and pressure for a high pressure film [2].

For a quantitative analyse of a pressure print a video-optical solution set-up and the software-system FADIE has been developed¹.

For a quantitative solution of a pressure print its necessary to make reference prints for several pressure sizes all over the pressure-range of the film. For getting a representative curve of the relation between colouring and pressure minimum 6 pressure prints are necessary. The principle run of the solution is represented in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8: Routine of a pressure-film analyse.

The film-analyse gets started normally with a video print of the neutral point. With that plotting incorrect measurements as a result of the illumination situation will be eliminated. Every calibration and pressure print has to be corrected with that neutral print. FADIE has a module which generates a reference-line of nth order, out of the 6 or more reference prints. For every film-typ the completed gray colour graduation is placed at disposal. In the last step different gray tints have a colour to be assigned to. The gray tints partition can, but have not to be linear. In the second step the analyse of the pressure film will be done. The software assigns every pixel, corresponding to the gray tint, a colour.

¹ The software FADIE is a product of COMPULOG CORP., BÖBLINGEN, GERMANY.

Fig. 9 shows the pressure print (high pressure film) and the resulted colour print, done with FADIE.

Fig. 9: Contact pressure prints for a polygon form $d_m = 56.5$ mm, $e = 3.25$, $n = 3$, fitting length = 60 mm, $M_T = 200$ Nm, $M_V = 35$ Nm.

FADIE has a lot of features for the data-processing. For example the graph representation of the contact pressure at a marked position of the film, or the middle pressure value of the completed film.

The figure 10 represents the pressure-curves at different length positions of the fitting (see Fig. 10).

Plot A: Pressure curve for a pre-stress moment 55 Nm.

Plot B: Pressure curve of a torque moment $M_T = 500$ Nm.

Plot C: Pressure curve of a pre-stress moment of $M_V = 55$ Nm and $M_T = 500$ Nm.

Fig. 10: Presented are plots of the contact pressure curve (fitting-length: 60 mm).

The comparison of the curves shows that the type of the pressure curve as a result of the torque-moment, is changed by the pre-stress moment. The pressure-curve of a pre-stressed fitting can be found through a superposition of the torque moment pressure line and the pre-stress moment pressure line.

5. CONCLUSION

Tests have been done with GFRP- and CFRP-tubes. The cross-section of tube-type 1 was circular formed in the center part and polygonal in the fitting range and the second tube-type was polygonal over all. Tests with nonpre-stressed fitting-elements show, that it's possible to transmit torque moments safe. To increase the maximum torque the splitted pre-stressed fitting elements have been developed. The tests showed that very high torque moments can be transmitted if high contact pressures are realized, by low quotients of $A\epsilon/\epsilon_0$. Fig. 11 represents a twist-moment diagram for adhered, plugged and pre-stressed polygonal connections.

Fig. 11: Torque loop for different kinds of fitting (PQ_2).

6. REFERENCES

- [1] Fortuna. Wissenswertes über Polygonverbindungen. FORTUNA-Werke, Stuttgart-Bad Cannstatt, Deutschland.
- [2] Fuji prescale film, FUJI PHOTO FILM CO. LTD, Tokyo, Japan.

Special thanks to Mr. M. Mühlenkamp for his help.